

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

Call: H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-2020 (*Digital transformation in Health and Care*)

Topic: SC1-DTH-06-2020 (*Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices*)

Grant agreement No: 101017578

Deliverable 2.3

Communication channels and materials

Due date of delivery: 30 June 2024

Actual submission date: 28 June 2024

Start of the project: 1 January 2021

End date: 30 June 2024

Reference

Name	SIMCor_D2.3 Communication channels and materials_LYN_28-06-2024
Lead beneficiary	Lynkeus (LYN)
Author(s)	Gaia Reale, Anna Rizzo (LYN)
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Report
Official delivery date	30 June 2024
Date of validation by the WP Leader	28 June 2024
Date of validation by the Coordinator	28 June 2024
Signature of the Coordinator	28 June 2024

Version log

Issue date	Version	Involved	Comments
07/06/2024	1.0	Gaia Reale (LYN)	First draft by LYN
07/06/2024	2.0	Anna Rizzo (LYN)	Internal review by LYN
21/06/2024	3.0	Jan Brüning (CHA), Roberta De Michele, Janaki Raman (VPH)	Internal review by CHA and VPH
27/06/2024	4.0	Jan Brüning (CHA)	Project Coordinator's review
28/06/2024	5.0	Anna Rizzo (LYN)	Final review and formal checking by LYN
28/06/2024	Final	Gaia Reale (LYN)	Submission by PC

Executive summary

The purpose of this document is to report on SIMCor communication channels, the strategy to produce communication and dissemination materials and the corresponding activities during the implementation of the project. These include the web channels, i.e., the website, LinkedIn, X, YouTube and Zenodo, along with the analysis of web channel analytics and metrics and the publicity campaigns, and the printed materials used to present the project at events, workshops, conferences and focus groups, as well as a brief overview of the produced peer-reviewed and generalist publications.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CHA	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin
C&D	Communication and dissemination
BIO	Biotronik
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IHS	Institute for Advanced Studies Vienna
LYN	Lynkeus Srl
M	Month
PHI	Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.
PIs	Principal Investigators
TAVI	Transcatheter aortic valve implantation
TUG	Graz University of Technology
UCL	University College London
VPH	Virtual Physiological Human Institute
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Introduction

SIMCor aims to create a computational platform for in-silico-based development, validation and regulatory approval of cardiovascular implantable devices, as an open resource for collaborative research and development between device manufacturers, researchers, medical authorities and regulators.

This goal was achieved thanks to the support of a community of interest including relevant groups in research, clinics and industry. The aim of such engagement was not only to raise awareness of the methods and resources developed, but more importantly to increase trust in the reliability of in-silico testing solutions to achieve robust validation of medical devices, leading to safer and more effective devices, and with improved time-to-market and cost efficiency.

SIMCor has endeavoured to provide the potential user communities and society with comprehensive information on its rationale, activity and results. Consistently, the project *communication and dissemination* (C&D) strategy aimed to engage with a range of diverse stakeholders, including **(1) the ICT and healthcare business and research community, (2) the medical device industry, (3) regulators and standardisation committees, (4) clinical cardiology community, (5) patients and their associations, (6) mass media, policy makers and society** at large.

These target groups were categorised as follows: **(a) primary target groups**, to be addressed for dissemination and exploitation of results; **(b) secondary target groups**, to be included for public discussions, citizen science approaches and general communication.

The project C&D was articulated into 3 phases, that are described as follows:

- **Phase I (M1-M12)** was a preparatory phase in which the foundations for the actual activity were laid by formulating the overall C&D strategy, analysing the project stakeholder groups and relevant audiences, assessing the consortium's partner networks, as well as creating project branding, communication channels and tools, while conducting the initial community building and general communication.
- **Phase II (M13-M30)** was dedicated to the actual dissemination of the results through publications and events, the production of communication content based on stakeholder involvement and the expansion and consolidation of the audience.
- In **Phase III (M31-M42)**, the last year of the project, the consortium conducted the dissemination of its final results through peer-review publications and conferences, finalised the interaction with sister projects, regulatory and notified bodies, obtaining essential feedback on in-silico solutions, and the exploitation planning activity was finalised.

Figure 1: SIMCor C&D phases.

The Communication utilised 5 online communication channels, including **the SIMCor website, LinkedIn, X, YouTube and Zenodo**. Some of the social media contents include, among others:

- The **SIMCor in-silico medicine glossary** and the **'Pills of in-silico medicine' video series**, that were designed to make the general public familiar with in-silico medicine related concepts and terminologies.
- **Project research achievements**, such as publication of new **journal articles** or **demo videos** on project tools.
- **Dissemination** events, such as **conferences or workshops** the consortium organised or participated in, as well as related **advertising campaigns** designed to generate website traffic and convert it into event engagement.

Multimedia includes the extensive video production collected on the SIMCor channel on YouTube and the media content produced by the *Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPH)* as a joint effort of SIMCor and the InSilicoWorld project.

Printed materials such as brochures, posters and roll-ups, pens and notebooks were also produced.

Publications such as journal articles, conference papers and book chapters were widely disseminated, and additional ones are in preparation and will be published after the end of the project.

Web channels

Website

Figure 2: SIMCor website homepage.

Structure and contents

The project website¹ was released at the beginning of M4 and is divided into 6 sections, i.e., *About, Consortium, Publications & materials, News, Related projects and Contact*.

About

This page offers an overview of the project, passing through its rationale, mission and strategic objectives, clinical use cases, implementation phases and expected impacts.

Figure 3: SIMCor website 'About' section.

¹ <https://www.simcor-h2020.eu>

Consortium

This page illustrates the consortium composition, including a brief description of consortium partners, their role in the project and their reference contact.

Figure 4: SIMCor website 'Consortium' section.

Publication & materials

This section showcases all project-produced materials, ranging from peer-reviewed publications (journal articles, conference papers, book chapters) to presentations, public deliverables, multimedia (teaser video, demos), press releases and communication materials.

The website grants open access to all peer-reviewed publications via the publisher’s website (‘gold’ open access) or via the SIMCor Community in Zenodo. Zenodo² is an open science repository, as described in the associated paragraph, that enables the creation of open access data collections, namely ‘communities’. SIMCor has utilised the Zenodo community to deposit public deliverables, paper manuscripts, reports, presentations and other materials produced as part of the project.

Figure 5: SIMCor website ‘Publications & materials’ page.

News

The section contains all project-related news, including major research achievements, project meetings, research developments, and dissemination events, such as conferences, workshops, and symposia.

Figure 6: SIMCor website ‘News’ section.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/simcor/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Related projects

This section constitutes a showcase for sister projects with similar research and development goals, with whom SIMCor is collaborating, such as *EDITH*, *InSilicoWorld*, *SimCardioTest*, *SimInSitu*.

EDITH

RELATED PROJECTS

European Virtual Human Twin

EDITH is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), funded by the European Commission, which will capitalise on the developments of digital technologies, high-performance computing, availability and access to research and healthcare data in Europe, with the mission of defining a roadmap to go from separated single organ systems, to data-driven and knowledge-driven fully integrated multiscale and multiorgan whole-body twin. EDITH will facilitate this process by building an evolutionary ecosystem, driven by a consensus among the relevant European communities, and implemented through the aid of practical tools, such as a data/model repository (within the scope of EDITH), and a simulation platform (to be implemented after EDITH).

Start date: **1 October 2022** | End date: **30 September 2024** | Coordinating institution:

Figure 7: SIMCor website 'Related projects' section paragraph featuring the EDITH project.

InSilicoWorld

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials

The In Silico World project aims at accelerating the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies used for the development and regulatory assessment of medicines and medical devices, by lowering seven identified barriers: development, validation, accreditation, optimisation, exploitation, information, and training. Our vision is a future where medical products, thanks to the use of modelling and simulation, are developed much faster and with the highest possible safety standards.

Start date: **1 January 2021** | End date: **31 December 2024** | Coordinating institution:

Figure 8: SIMCor website 'Related projects' section paragraph featuring the InSilicoWorld project.

SimCardioTest

Simulation of Cardiac Devices & Drugs for in-silico Testing and Certification

SimCardioTest aims to design new predictive tools in cardiac pathologies and aims to accelerate the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices. One objective is to provide a framework and wide approach of in-silico methods (computer modelling and simulation) where generic and standardized elements can be used for other applications. The second one aims to demonstrate that such approach can help develop devices and drugs as well as reduce the cost and time to market and gain the trust of scientists, companies, regulatory bodies, physicians, and patients. The final objective is to impact the whole clinical trials, since this approach can replace some invasive aspects of these trials, and maybe provide novel biomarkers for more accurate clinical trials.

Start date: **1 January 2021** | End date: **31 December 2024** | Coordinating institution:

Inria

Figure 9: SIMCor website 'Related projects' section paragraph featuring the SimCardioTest project.

SimInSitu

In-silico development and clinical trial platform for testing in-situ tissue engineered heart valves

SimInSitu promises the first in-silico clinical trial platform to predict the short- and long-term response of in-situ tissue engineered heart valves (TEHV) in humans. We will enable the simultaneous assessment and optimization of the performance and safety of TEHV by a multidisciplinary approach combining advanced patient-specific computational models, tissue and growth remodelling algorithms, and dedicated device models. SimInSitu will not only develop computer models but will also verify and validate them thoroughly by making use of in-vitro and in-vivo data and, where necessary, will generate new data to support the credibility of in-silico clinical trials.

Start date: **1 January 2021** | End date: **31 December 2024** | Coordinating institution:

4RealSim

Figure 10: SIMCor website 'Related projects' section paragraph featuring the SimInSitu project.

Contact

This form was designed as a contact point for information requests on the project, collaboration proposals, and others.

The screenshot shows the SIMCor website's contact form. The header is dark blue with the SIMCor logo on the left and navigation links: ABOUT, CONSORTIUM, PUBLICATIONS & MATERIALS, NEWS, RELATED PROJECTS, and CONTACT. The main content area is light blue and contains a contact form with the following fields:

- Name* (required)
- E-mail* (required)
- Subject
- Message (large text area)

Below the form, there is a checkbox for data processing authorization:

I authorize the processing of my personal data in accordance with art. 13 GDPR 679/16 – "General Data Protection Regulation". The provided data will be exclusively used for the defined purposes and not be disclosed to any third party.

Figure 11: SIMCor website 'Contact' section.

Analytics data

(Source: Google Analytics - Reference period: 1 January 2021 – 12 June 2024)

Acquisition overview

- Total users: 4.2K
- Total users (including one-time users): 4.5K

The SIMCor website, officially launched on **7 April 2021**, managed to reach a total of **4,457 visitors** (*New users*, i.e., the number of users who interacted with the website for the first time), **4,185 of whom are returning visitors** (*Users*, i.e., the total number of active users), in the **reference period (1 January 2021 – 12 June 2024)**. These have an average of **5.758 sessions/user** (i.e., the number of sessions that began on the website), and an average of **8.59 views/session** (i.e., the number of web pages viewed by users per session. Repeated views of a single page or screen are counted). Given the website has no marketing purpose, the revenue of the website is euro 0. These users have an **average engagement time of 3m 37s**.

Audience name +	↓ Users	New users	Sessions	Views per session	Average session duration	Total revenue
	4,185 100% of total	4,457 100% of total	5,758 100% of total	8.59 Avg 0%	4m 42s Avg 0%	€0.00
1 All Users	4,185	4,457	5,758	8.59	4m 42s	€0.00

Figure 12: Acquisition overview for the SIMCor website in the reference period (1 January 2021 - 12 June 2024).

Figure 13: SIMCor website user acquisition over time in the reference period (1 January 2021 - 12 June 2024).

First reporting period (1 January 2021 – 30 June 2022)

In the first period, an initial audience of 1,154 users was reached, most of them (1,149) new users. The only audience peak (>50 users/day) registered was Wednesday 7 April (58 users), the day of the website launch.

Figure 14: SIMCor website user acquisition over time in the first reporting period (1 January 2021 - 30 June 2022).

Second reporting period (1 July 2022 – 31 December 2023)

In the second period, the audience of 2,463 new users was reached, 2,361 of them returning users. Audience peaks (>50 users/day) were reached on Saturday 12 August (372 users), Friday 2 September (241 users), Wednesday 4 October (66 users) and Wednesday 6 December (87 users), in correspondence to the launch of the INNOVAHEART 2024 registration campaign and the INNOVAHEART website.

Figure 15: SIMCor website user acquisition over time in the second reporting period (1 July 2022 – 31 December 2023).

Third reporting period (1 January – 30 June 2024)

In the third and last period, which starts on 1 January and ends on 12 June 2024, at the time of the preparation of this report, the audience of 845 new users was reached, 832 of them returning users. Audience peaks (>50 users/day) were reached on Wednesday 7 February (217 users), on Day 2 of the INNOVAHEART 2024 workshop, on Sunday 3 March (73 users) and Sunday 2 June (88 users).

Figure 16: SIMCor website user acquisition over time in the third reporting period (1 January - 12 June 2024).

User acquisition sources

A large portion of website users (1,621) reached the website by direct search, which means they already knew the address, another large portion (1,436) by referral, coming from other websites, a third large portion (1,326) through organic search by search engines, and only a minority (74) through social media referral. This emphasises the importance of cross-dissemination among sister projects, institutions and initiatives.

First user prim...channel group) ▾ +	↓ New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	Event count All events ▾
	4,457 100% of total	2,982 100% of total	51.79% Avg 0%	0.71 Avg 0%	3m 30s Avg 0%	78,641 100% of total
1 Direct	1,621	1,558	47.85%	0.95	1m 31s	22,728
2 Referral	1,436	169	55.41%	0.15	9m 10s	41,290
3 Organic Search	1,326	1,236	56.44%	0.93	1m 11s	14,071
4 Organic Social	74	47	54.65%	0.64	41s	541
5 Unassigned	0	0	0%	0.00	36s	11

Figure 17: Overview of user acquisition sources in the reference period (1 January 2021 – 12 June 2024).

Geographic distribution

Users by countries

Unsurprisingly, the majority of website users comes from the United States (577 users), where several researchers in in-silico medicine come from, and Europe, particularly from consortium partners' countries, such as Germany (531 users), Netherlands (351 users), Italy (317 users), France (296 users), Austria (215 users), United Kingdom (176 users), and Belgium (135 users). However, a significant number of visitors was also registered from China (117 users) and Canada (106 users).

Figure 18: Overview of the geographical distribution of website users in the reference period (1 January 2021 – 12 June 2024).

Conclusive remarks

A series of conclusions could be drawn from such data. Firstly, acquisition of website visitors is not a trivial task, especially for research projects interesting a 'niche' of specialists like SIMCor. However, the presence of live contents, like participation to conferences and workshops, especially when accompanied by social media campaigns, can give a strong contribution to widen its audience. Likewise, networking and cross-dissemination with other sister projects, institutions and communities can give a strong boost to the website traffic, and this nicely aligns with the current emphasis of most Horizon call topics on foreseeing such activities as part of the workplan. If budget allows, the use of paid campaigns could also further support audience building. As far as the geographic distribution of visitors is concerned, the visitors' distribution was not limited to the consortium partners' countries, indicating that a good C&D strategy, with synergy among different communication channels and tools, can be successful in reaching new audiences, in the same research community and beyond, unrelated to project participants.

X

Contents

The SIMCor editorial schedule consists of 1-2 posts per week. These contents encompass:

- News on events
 - Conferences
 - Workshops
 - Project meetings
 - Symposia.

Other than announcing the events, the profile included social live posting of poster presentations and talks in real time.
- Multimedia
 - Project teaser video
 - ‘Pills of in-silico medicine’ video series
 - Demos of project tools
 - ‘SIMCor: an overview’ project final video.
- Glossary of in-silico terminologies.

The SIMCor glossary of in-silico terminology is aimed at citizens to understand and clarify scientific concepts and terms and to increase confidence in in-silico medicine.
- Journal articles published by consortium partners.

This content was aimed at a wide audience, ranging from citizens, not yet familiar with in-silico medicine concepts, to researchers, clinicians or industry members looking for information on the status of the project.

The selected project channels were LinkedIn and X. Both channels are suitable for high-level communication to layman audiences as well as for engagement with professionals, institutional pages of industries, universities and EU-funded projects.

Among social media channels, they are certainly the ones least dedicated to entertainment and where people are more likely to inform themselves, network and, in the case of LinkedIn, offer or seek work.

SIMCor's glossary

SIMCor's glossary is a specialised set of content for LinkedIn and X that explains SIMCor technical concepts and vocabulary, such as, among others, *digital twins*, *virtual cohorts*, *computational modelling and simulation*, *verification and validation*.

Figure 19: SIMCor X and LinkedIn posts on the SIMCor in-silico glossary.

Dissemination events

Live posting on social media is a live activity during the events that captures relevant highlights of the event and the specific contribution of consortium partners through photos or short videos.

Figure 20: SIMCor live social posting during the FDA/MDIC and DGBMT events.

'Pills of in-silico medicine' video series

The video series is very similar to the SIMCor glossary, both to make scientific topics more understandable and familiar and to appeal to the target audience. The episodes illustrate key scientific concepts and research strategies of the project and the in-silico medicine field at large.

Figure 21: 'Pills of in-silico medicine' series posts.

Research results and publications

This type of content is used to inform the SIMCor audience about the latest research results of the project.

Figure 22: X post on the development status of the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and LinkedIn post announcing a new article published by the consortium.

Profile layout

The SIMCor X page was launched in M1 and was weekly updated according to the editorial schedule producing at least 1 post per week. Content in X is limited to a maximum of 280 characters per post, hence it consists of high-level updates that require little time to read and are suited for users that are not familiar with technical topics to get some insights on project related contents.

The image shows a screenshot of the SIMCor X profile page. At the top, there is a blue header with the SIMCor logo on the left and an "Edit profile" button on the right. Below the header, the profile name "SIMCor" and handle "@SIMCor_EU" are displayed. The bio reads: "An H2020 RIA establishing a computational platform for in-silico development, validation and regulatory approval of cardiovascular implantable devices". It also includes a brief description: "Non-Governmental & Nonprofit Organization" and "Joined January 2021". Below the bio, it shows "248 Following 161 Followers".

The main content area is titled "Tweets" and shows a pinned tweet from SIMCor (@SIMCor_EU) dated 17/07/23. The tweet text is: "Great news! #SIMCor #H2020 has obtained a 6-month extension by the @EU_Commission to consolidate and expand its work on #cardiovascular #modelling and #simulation, #virtualcohorts and #insilicotrials in #cardiology. Check out our mission 📌 youtube.com/watch?v=pegGzJ...". Below the text is a large blue image featuring the SIMCor logo and a stylized human figure with a heart, surrounded by data points and a checkmark icon. At the bottom of the tweet, there are icons for replies, retweets, and likes (5).

Figure 23: SIMCor X homepage.

Analytics data

The SIMCor X channel, which was officially launched in **January 2021**, has total of 168 followers as **organic reach**. The X analysis period is the last year of activity, the X analysis platform can record a maximum of 365 days. The X profile had a considerable response of reactions and impressions in the last year and a half of the project, i.e., from January 2023 to June 2024, when the constant publication of content allowed the algorithm to keep the attention of our followers active. The following screenshots show the highlights of the project period.

First reporting period (1 January 2021 – 30 June 2022)

During this period, the SIMCor X profile had a limited amount of interactions, e.g., re-sharing posts, comments, probably due to the relative scarcity of project results. For this reason, there was little incentive for the algorithm to display the few posts published on the site.

Figure 24: Metrics of the first reporting period (1 January 2021 - 30 June 2022).

Second reporting period (1 July 2022 – 31 December 2023)

In the second reporting period, the profile started to follow an editorial schedule and constant regular publication. Although SIMCor is a niche topic, the constant and regular publication of content and the numerosity of events, publications and multimedia production has enabled greater audience interaction and engagement, enabling the algorithm to display our content more consistently.

Figure 25: Metrics of the second reporting period (1 July 2022 - 31 December 2023).

Third reporting period (1 January – 30 June 2024)

In the third reporting period, the profile continued its positive trend, also thanks to the INNOVAHEART event and the emerging of project final results.

Figure 26: metrics about the third reporting period (1 January - 30 June 2024).

LinkedIn

Contents

The contents of the LinkedIn editorial schedule were the same of X, however leveraging the higher number of characters allowed by LinkedIn, with longer and more informative descriptions.

Profile layout

The SIMCor LinkedIn page³ was launched in April 2022 (M16), as it was not foreseen in the original C&D plan. However, the consortium considered advantageous to add an additional channel focused on research, innovation and business development, to potentially increase its audience.

LinkedIn is used to find or offer job opportunities and promote one's career and project activities. For an EU-funded project like SIMCor, LinkedIn was considered a suitable channel to potentially enlarge its network of researchers, clinicians, and regulators. The presences of institutional profiles of universities and hospitals allows to connect with institutional profiles rather than individuals only. For this reason, LinkedIn was ideal to network with other sister projects and promote workshops, scientific conferences, symposia, etc.

SIMCor also used LinkedIn to create paid advertising campaigns for the INNOVAHEART 2024 workshop. The *advertising campaign* is a set of advertisements that work together to promote a product or service, in this case the workshop. It is designed around a specific and unique theme to create brand awareness for a product or service among the target groups identified by the algorithm. The advertising campaign encourages this target group to register for an event or attend a workshop. The LinkedIn algorithm finds the selected target group.

Figure 27: SIMCor LinkedIn homepage.

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/simcor-h2020/?viewAsMember=true>

Analytics data

(Source: LinkedIn Analytics - Reference period: June 2023 – 19 June 2024)

The SIMCor LinkedIn, officially launched in **June 2022**, totalized 270 followers as an **organic audience** and **181 new followers** in the last 365 days. Organic audience is an **active audience**, meaning that all profile traffic came from interaction with the profiles of SIMCor followers and the profiles that SIMCor follows. The organic audience differs from the **sponsored audience**, which is the one that arrives on the SIMCor profile thanks to a paid campaign. The LinkedIn algorithm is incentivised to send inputs to the selected suitable destination to get more engagement or traffic on the page. LinkedIn's analysis period is the last year of activity, so the following screenshots have represented the analysis of the longest possible period, one year, from M31 to M42.

Content

The content refers to the interaction with posts and videos on the SIMCor LinkedIn page. From June 2023 to June 2024, there were a total of **810 reactions**, **15 comments** and **18 reposts** on the SIMCor page.

LinkedIn **reactions** are a series of expressions that provide a way for members to more easily engage in conversations and communicate with their network. **Comments** are the appreciations or questions that followers leave in the comments section under the post. With **reposts**, followers publish posts from other members or LinkedIn pages and add their own ideas or questions to share with their network.

Figure 28: LinkedIn highlights.

SIMCor used a sponsored campaign on LinkedIn for the first and only time to promote the INNOVAHEART 2024 workshop, from December 2023 to January 2024. Despite the advertisement for the workshop, the sponsored campaign was useful also for the **brand awareness** of SIMCor, the LinkedIn page totalized **312,344 impressions**, and therefore way more than the **33,398 of organic impressions**.

Figure 29: LinkedIn visitors metrics of M30-M42.

Visitors

From June 2023 to June 2024, the LinkedIn page had 1258 views and 448 visitors. The main attraction were the posts during the consortium meeting and the social live posts during events such as conferences and symposia, some posts on journal articles, some posts on the SIMCor glossary and the ‘Pills of in-silico medicine’ series, or the sponsored campaign for INNOVAHEART 2024.

Figure 30: LinkedIn visitor highlights of M30-M42.

Followers

Throughout the project period, the main work on the LinkedIn page was organic, with no sponsored campaigns, and from June 2023 to June 2024 the page had a total of 187 more followers than in the previous period.

Figure 31: LinkedIn followers highlights and metrics of M30-M42 (June 2023-June 2024).

Demographic distribution - Users by countries

The majority of profile followers comes from the consortium partners' countries, such as Germany (5.7% followers), Netherlands (4.9% followers), France (4.5% followers), United Kingdom (3.8% followers), Spain (2.6% followers), Italy (3% followers), and Belgium (2,6% followers).

Figure 32: LinkedIn followers' demographic metrics of M30-M42 (June 2023-June 2024).

Demographic distribution - Users by job functions

Most followers come from research (17%), education (15.9%), engineering (10.7%), information technology (5.2%), business development (4.8%), healthcare (4.1%), sales (3.3%), media and communications (3%), programme and project management (3%) and operations (2.2%).

Figure 33: LinkedIn followers' demographic metrics of M30-M42 (June 2023-June 2024).

Demographic distribution - Users by industry

Industries include research services (17.8%), medical device manufacturing (15.6%), higher education (15.6%), IT services and consulting (5.9%), hospitals and healthcare (5.6%), pharmaceutical manufacturing (3.7%), software development (3.3%), business consulting and services (3.3%), biotechnology research (3.3%) and industrial machinery manufacturing (1.9%).

Figure 34: LinkedIn followers' demographic metrics of M30-M42 (June 2023-June 2024).

Conclusive remarks

From the progress analysis of these three years, it can be concluded that constant activity and a good diversification of content produces good results in terms of visibility and awareness of the project's existence. Due to the way the algorithms of social channels work at this historical moment, it would be appropriate to dedicate an economic part to the constant presence of an advertising campaign that increasingly disseminates this content outside the circle of consortium partners.

INNOVAHEART website

INNOVAHEART 2024 was the 2nd edition of the workshop jointly organised by the namesake group of sister projects in in-silico cardiology. It took place on 6-7 February 2024, in Leuven, Belgium, and was jointly organised by SIMCor, SimInSitu, SimCardioTest, EDITH and inEurHeart, with the support of KU Leuven, which hosted the event.

The event focus was *'Translation of in-silico models into clinical application'*, with key themes and open challenges discussed through working groups and keynote talks. The event addressed industry, regulatory authorities, scientists and clinicians, among others. Its website, though not SIMCor-specific, is reported here as the SIMCor consortium was entrusted with its design, development and maintenance, as well as with the entire event communication strategy, and will remain as the reference website for the event and beyond.

Figure 35: INNOVAHEART website landing page.

The website was developed in a single interface. The menu highlighted in the top bar allow the user to scroll down the landing page to immediately reach the desired topic. The subsections of the landing page are shown below.

About

The section that describes the aims of the workshop.

Figure 36: INNOVAHEART landing page 'About' section.

Organisers and speakers

The section containing all speakers of the workshop and their presentations as well as the organisers of INNOVAHEART 2024.

Figure 37: INNOVAHEART landing page 'Organisers and speakers' section.

1st Edition

The section includes the video of the first edition of the workshop, organised under the lead of SimCardioTest, that took place in Bordeaux in March 2023.

Figure 38: INNOVAHEART landing page 'First edition section'.

INNOVAHEART campaigns

LinkedIn and X

The communication campaign for the workshop took place on SIMCor social channels, that in turn were shared by the sister projects' social media channels. An advertising campaign was created on LinkedIn to address and engage the coherent target groups (examples are shown below). The main topics of the communication campaign were the programme and the objectives of the workshop, as well as the speakers' presentations.

Figure 39: INNOVAHEART X content.

SIMCor
264 followers
3mo · Edited · 🌐

#Innovaheart2024, Leuven On day 1 we will discuss with Nils Götzen (4RS), Liesbet Geris (VPHi), Oscar Camara (UPF) about verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification: approaches are advantagi ...see more

**INNOVAHEART
2024**

Assessing the credibility of in-silico models

Nils Götzen
4RS

Liesbet Geris
VPHi

Oscar Camara
Universitat Pompeu
Fabra

Figure 40: INNOVAHEART on LinkedIn - speakers of the event.

Figure 41: INNOVAHEART LinkedIn advertising campaign.

The advertising campaign lasted 1 month and was a conversion campaign with a call-to-action button that invited people to register and led them to the landing page of the workshop. The campaign started on 20 December 2023 and ended on 31 January 2024. The results in terms of clicks were around 1,700 clicks on the INNOVAHEART landing page.

INNOVAHEART advertising campaign analytics

LinkedIn campaign for INNOVAHEART was an advertising campaign to convert the engagement into workshop participants. A **conversion** is when a user performs a desired action in response to a call-to-action placed in an announcement. The campaign was launched in December 2023 until January 2024, one month before the event. The structured campaign included an image of the INNOVAHEART logo, a text explaining the workshop's design and contents, and a "call to action" with a link to the INNOVAHEART landing page. Key results included the website visits and impressions. The campaign achieved over 1,700 website visits and 312,000 impressions.

Search by name, ID, or type

Filters(2) Columns: Performance Breakdown Time range: 12/1/2023 - 1/31/2024

Campaign Name	Off/On	Status	Key Results	Campaign Group
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 selected campaign	-	-	-	-
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> INNOVAHEART_Website visits ID: 287288963 - Sponsored Content	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Completed	1,727 Website Visits (0%)	InnovaHeart

: Performance Breakdown Time range: 12/1/2023 -

Impressions	Clicks	Average CTR
312,344	1,727	0.55%
312,344 (0%)	1,727 (0%)	0.55% (0%)

Figure 42: LinkedIn results of the advertising campaign.

YouTube

The SIMCor YouTube channel serves as a showcase and repository for the multimedia content and includes the all-video production such as the video teaser, the ‘Pills of in-silico medicine’ series, video demos of project tools, final video and its trailer. Exemplary multimedia productions are shown below.

The screenshot shows the SIMCor YouTube channel page. At the top left is the SIMCor logo, a stylized blue and green circuit-like icon. To its right is the channel name 'SIMCor' in bold black text, followed by the handle '@simcor5252', subscriber count '17 iscritti', and video count '12 video'. Below this is a bio: 'SIMCor is a 3-year (2021-2023) Horizon 2020 research and innovation action developing a ...' and a search icon. A black 'Iscriviti' button is positioned below the bio. The navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Video', 'Playlist', and 'Community'. The main content area is titled 'Per te' and features three video thumbnails. The first two are from the 'PILLS OF IN-SILICO MEDICINE' series: '02 VIRTUAL PATIENT COHORTS' (6:39) and '04 IN-SILICO TRIAL PERSPECTIVES' (5:38). The third is a 'SIMCor VRE Demo' (7:19) with 17 views and posted 5 months ago. A blue call-to-action card reads '01. Register a new user account in VRE' with a right arrow. A small SIMCor logo and video icon are visible in the bottom right corner of the video area.

SIMCor
@simcor5252 · 17 iscritti · 12 video
SIMCor is a 3-year (2021-2023) Horizon 2020 research and innovation action developing a ... >

Iscriviti

Home Video Playlist Community

Per te

PILLS OF IN-SILICO MEDICINE
02 VIRTUAL PATIENT COHORTS
6:39

PILLS OF IN-SILICO MEDICINE
04 IN-SILICO TRIAL PERSPECTIVES
5:38

SIMCor VRE Demo
17 visualizzazioni · 5 mesi fa

01. Register a new user account in VRE

Figure 43: SIMCor YouTube homepage.

Zenodo

Zenodo⁴ is an open science repository developed by the OpenAire project of the European Commission, which allows to create open access file collections, namely ‘Communities’. The consortium opened a SIMCor dedicated community and used it to deposit public deliverables, paper manuscripts, reports, presentations, and other materials produced in the project. The links to the deposited materials was used to showcase them via the website, X and LinkedIn.

The screenshot displays the SIMCor community page on Zenodo. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The main header identifies the community as 'SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular Implantable devices)' and includes a 'New upload' button. Below this, there are filters for 'Records', 'Members', 'Curation policy', and 'About'. The search results section shows '55 results found' and a 'Sort by' dropdown set to 'Newest'. Two records are listed:

- Record 1:** 'SIMCor. Deliverable 4.3 - SOPs for virtual cohorts generation and validation (TUE, M36)'. It is dated 'December 27, 2023 (v1)', marked as a 'Project deliverable', and is 'Open'. The authors are Huberts, Wouter; Verstraeten, Sabine; Lesage, Raphaëlle, and 6 others. The description states it provides a standard operating procedure (SOP) for virtual cohorts. It has 53 views and 2 downloads.
- Record 2:** 'SIMCor. Deliverable 8.7 - Reduced-order model (PHI, M30)'. It is dated 'June 29, 2023 (v1)', marked as a 'Project deliverable', and is 'Open'. The authors are Spanjaards, Michelle; Divi, Sai; Verhoosel, Clemens, and 1 other. It has 41 views and 9 downloads.

Figure 44: SIMCor Zenodo homepage.

The SIMCor community in Zenodo includes the following items, along with the number of views (n° of views of the item in Zenodo) and the downloads (n° of downloads of the item from Zenodo):

- 41 Publications
 - Views: **2517**
 - Downloads: **1784**
- 6 Presentations
 - Views: **466**
 - Downloads: **294**
- 5 Video/Audio
 - Views: **165**
 - Downloads: **16**
- 1 Dataset
 - Views: **197**
 - Downloads: **85**
- 1 Poster
 - Views: **36**
 - Downloads: **31**
- 1 Software
 - Views: **72**
 - Downloads: **7**

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/simcor/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Multimedia

SIMCor multimedia include the extensive video productions collected on the SIMCor YouTube channel and the media content produced by the Virtual Human Institute (VPH) in collaboration with InSilicoWorld, as illustrated below.

Teaser

This video, entitled '*SIMCor: in-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices*' provides a high-level overview of the project, its goals and expected impacts.

Figure 45: Overview of SIMCor video teaser.

Demo videos of project tools

Several demos, in the form of short videos describing and visualizing relevant procedures, have been generated and made available on the SIMCor YouTube channel.

Figure 46: Demo of TAVI device implantation simulations and the VRE.

Figure 47: R-Statistical environment and on clinically driven Virtual Cohort Generator for aortic valve geometries.

Figure 48: Demo of fast-to-evaluate surrogate models used for device implantation and video on virtual cohort generation for in-silico trials of transcatheter aortic valve implantation.

'Pills of In-silico medicine' series

The video series *'Pills of in-silico medicine'* aims to introduce some of the key concepts of in-silico medicine to improve the SIMCor audience's confidence and awareness of in-silico medicine. The videos also inform the SIMCor audience about the latest research results of the project.

Figure 49: video 'Pills of In-silico medicine'.

Final result overview (trailer and full video)

The video, entitled ‘SIMCor: an overview’, is a 13’ video that narrates the goals, activity and main results of the project through interviews with the Principal Investigators of all consortium partners, accompanied by animations, demos of project tools, and video shootings from the INNOVAHEART 2024 workshop. To enhance its visibility, a 3’ trailer was prepared and launched on 17 June, announcing the upcoming release of the full video. The full video was launched on 28 June via X and LinkedIn, as a conclusion of the project.

Figure 50: SIMCor video trailer.

‘Code & cure: understanding in-silico medicine’ video series

Our consortium partner VPH produced an insightful video series, entitled ‘Code & cure: understanding in-silico medicine’ as a joint dissemination effort among the SIMCor, SimCardioTest and ISW projects. The video series aims to spread the knowledge of in-silico medicine towards a larger public audience with animated videos, and covering several topics, spanning from models to real-world applications. While the aim of this series is similar to the one of the ‘Pills of in-silico medicine’, it is agnostic to any specific project.

VPH Institute
@VPHINST · 395 iscritti · 91 video
The Virtual Physiological Human Institute for Integrative Biomedical Research, in short VP... >
vph-institute.org
Iscriviti

Home **Video** Podcast Playlist

Più recenti Popolari Meno recenti

3rd episode Revolutionizing Healthcare: The Power of AI in Medicine
the **DIGITAL TWIN** theory
Podcast: with Leonardo **14:00**

Ep.03- Revolutionising healthcare: The power of AI in medicine (w/...)
30 visualizzazioni · 3 settimane fa

CODE & CURE
AI IN HEALTHCARE
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTHCARE
1:06

Episode 3: Artificial Intelligence in healthcare
71 visualizzazioni · 3 settimane fa

2nd EPISODE Modelling Medicine: how models work
the **DIGITAL TWIN** theory
Podcast: with Himanshu Kaul **12:40**

Ep. 02- Modelling Medicine: How models work (w/ Himanshu Kaul)
36 visualizzazioni · 1 mese fa

MEET THE VPHI YOUNG SCIENTISTS ANNA RAMELLA
3:08

A work of heart- An interview with Anna Ramella
19 visualizzazioni · 2 mesi fa

Figure 51: VPH Code and cure series.

Print-based materials

As part of the projects, many printed products such as leaflets, brochures and roll-ups were produced, as described below.

Leaflet

The leaflet is a one-page PDF providing an overview of SIMCor. It was used as a high-level presentation of the project for co-operations, partnerships, and advisory board meetings, among others.

SIMCor In-Silico testing and validation of **Cardiovascular Implantable** devices

www.simcor-h2020.eu
info@simcor.eu

Why SIMCor?

Verification and validation represent critical activities in the development lifecycle of implantable medical devices, due to the need to meet increasing clinical safety and performance standards set by constantly evolving regulations. In-silico methodologies, such as computer-based simulation and virtual patient cohorts, represent a promising opportunity for enhancing safety, efficacy, time and cost effectiveness of medical devices, but agreed standards and protocols are still needed for their full integration into the product cycle.

SIMCor aims to establish a computational platform for in-silico development, validation and regulatory approval of cardiovascular implantable devices, as a collaborative environment among device manufacturers, researchers, medical authorities and regulatory bodies.

The platform is composed of (1) a virtual cohort generation and validation domain and (2) a device implantation and effect simulation domain, and is equipped with a variety of in-silico modelling resources, including synthetic data, models and standard operating procedures.

VIRTUAL COHORT GENERATION & VALIDATION

SIMULATION OF DEVICE IMPLANTATION & PERFORMANCE

RESOURCES
Data, models, methodologies, standards, guidelines

Strategic objectives

Provide proof-of-validation for virtual cohorts and computer-based simulation of cardiovascular device implantation and performance

Develop standards and protocols for in-silico testing and validation of cardiovascular devices

Quantify the benefits of in-silico testing for healthcare, industry and society as a whole

Accelerate the integration of in-silico testing into the medical device regulatory approval process, the market and the clinics

Contribute to the European Open Science Cloud with data, virtual cohorts, simulation models, methodologies, standards and guidelines

Clinical focus

Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI)

TAVI is a less-invasive procedure, alternative to surgical replacement, for the treatment of aortic valve diseases, conditions where the valve cannot open and close properly, putting an extra strain on the heart.

Transcatheter aortic valves are made of cow or pig tissue, re-engineered and attached to a flexible expanding mesh frame. The valve is implanted by squeezing it around/inside a catheter, which is inserted and guided to the aortic valve. Once the new valve is implanted within the existing one, the catheter is removed and the new valve starts working.

Pulmonary artery pressure sensors (PAPS)

Heart failure is a medical condition where the heart muscle is unable to pump blood around the body properly, as it has become too weak or stiff due to narrowed arteries, high blood pressure, diabetes, obesity or other damaging conditions.

PAPS are implantable, wireless monitoring systems able to transmit information on the patient's blood flow dynamics and intra-cardiac pressure to caregivers. By enabling earlier intervention, PAPS have been shown to reduce hospitalisation and improve patients' quality of life.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101017578

Figure 52: SIMCor leaflet.

Brochure

The brochure provides a high-level overview of the rationale and aim of the project, its strategic objectives, clinical use cases and consortium partners. It was printed and distributed at events such as conferences, workshops and focus groups. It was translated in German for the 2nd focus group in Austria.

Figure 53: SIMCor brochure.

Roll-up poster

The roll-up, providing a visual overview of the project, was used during dissemination events, e.g., the VPH 2022 conference, the INNOVAHEART workshops, etc.

Figure 54: SIMCor roll-up poster.

Application scenarios on in-silico medicine

The SIMCor focus groups, held in London, United Kingdom and St. Pölten, Austria in May 2023 and March 2024, were organised as a joint effort of an interdisciplinary team including in-silico medicine researchers, sociologists, researchers in economics and science communication experts from consortium's partners *Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin* (CHA), *University College London* (UCL), the VPH, the *Institute for Advanced Studies* (IHS) and *Lynkeus* (LYN), leveraging the partners' experience on patient focus groups, also in the context of the InSilicoWorld project. The focus groups were multi-stakeholder discussion forums which explored the clinical, scientific, legal and ethical aspects of in-silico trials at the presence of researchers, healthcare professionals and patients.

To initiate and facilitate the discussion on in-silico medicine, some application scenarios were produced, with textual descriptions accompanied by original illustrations.

Clinical focus groups on in-silico medicine

Scenario: *In-silico trials to test for specific patient category and regulatory dossier*

VirtHeart is a medical technology company that develops cardiovascular devices. They want to know if there is a risk of blood leakage with their new prosthetic valve. If the prosthetic valve is not optimally adapted to the physiological geometry of the patient's heart, some blood could leak out at the edges and reduce the effectiveness of the valve.

To solve this problem, they have created a library of possible heart geometries based on medical images. From this, they reconstruct a variety of 3D geometries in the computer. They also create a computer model of the valve prosthesis that has the same physical properties and shape as that of the patient. With these computer-generated models, they can simulate different scenarios without animal or human testing and identify typical geometries or physiological characteristics that are associated with a higher or lower risk of leakage. In this way, they can determine the specific patient group for which the new valve optimally reduces the risk of leakage. In order to market the valve only for a specific patient category, the company must submit a dossier of evidence of efficacy and safety to the regulatory authorities. VirtHeart wants to use the above figures to justify and support the regulatory dossier.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101017578

Figure 55: SIMCor first in-silico application scenario.

Clinical focus groups on in-silico medicine

Scenario: *Computational model to determine and plan surgical interventions*

At Liverpool University Hospital, the cardiology team uses computer models to plan the actual valve replacement procedure. The procedure is a minimally invasive intervention that does not require open heart surgery (i.e., TAVI). The planning must be very precise. The computational models are virtual 3D reconstructions of the patient's heart. They take into account individual characteristics (mechanical and physiological) to predict how the heart will respond after surgery. Clinicians can then use a patient-specific model to determine, for example, the best type of heart valve to replace the defective valve, or to determine its size and shape. This means that important decisions about medical interventions are made based on information from the computational models.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101017578

Figure 56: SIMCor second in-silico application scenario.

Clinical focus groups on in-silico medicine

Scenario: *In-silico trials for reducing size of human trial populations and regulatory approval*

Future Cardiac Technologies is a company that has developed a new prosthetic heart valve that will be studied in a clinical trial. The company plans to include fewer patients than usual in this clinical trial because it will also conduct a virtual trial (or in-silico trial) using virtual patients and 3D computer models of the heart and the new prosthesis. The results of the human study and the virtual study will be compared. If the computer model is validated (i.e., if it shows similar results to real humans), the results of the human and virtual study are taken into account and further virtual patients are considered to complete the study and make a decision. If the computer model is not validated, it is abandoned for this study and only the results of a regular clinical trial (but then with more patients) are used for decision-making.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101017578

Figure 57: SIMCor third in-silico application scenario.

Publications

A comprehensive overview of produced publications (press releases, journal articles, conference papers and book chapters) is provided below. Further publications are in preparation.

Press release

A press release was issued on 15 January 2021 (M1), right after the project Kick-off meeting, to announce the beginning of the project, translated as necessary and disseminated by consortium partners press offices. The press release is available on the SIMCor website via Zenodo.

The screenshot displays a Zenodo file page for a SIMCor press release. The main content is a PDF viewer showing the following text:

SIMCor
PRESS RELEASE n.1/2021
15/01/2021 (for immediate release)

Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action kick-off:
SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices)

Berlin, 15 January 2021

Today, 15 January 2021, the Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin has concluded the kick-off e-meeting of the new EU-funded research project SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices). The project will create an in-silico platform and simulation tools for the development, validation and regulatory approval of cardiovascular devices, providing tangible value to patients and clinicians, device manufacturers, clinical researchers, medical authorities and regulatory bodies.

Cardiovascular implantable medical devices are among the most life-sustaining treatments in cardiology. According to the Regulatory Affairs Professionals Society, verification and validation are amongst the most critical activities in the medical development lifecycle. Inadequate validation is one of the most common issues leading to clinical complications, warnes from the US Food and Drug Administration and subsequent device

Below the PDF viewer, a file list shows:

Name	Size	Download all
SIMCor_pressrelease_01_projectstart&kickoff_15-01-2021.pdf md5:3775ecc34ced49fc92d2c7d267d3d69	201.6 kB	Preview Download

On the right side, there are several metadata sections:

- External resources:** Indexed in OpenAIRE.
- Communities:** SIMCor (In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices).
- Details:** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4446846; Resource type: Other; Publisher: Zenodo; Languages: English.
- Rights:** Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

Figure 58: SIMCor press release on Zenodo.

Peer-review publications

All journal articles, conference papers, and book chapters listed below have been produced by the project on M1-M42. In addition to those contents, other articles are currently in preparation and listed at the end of this section

Journal articles

N	Title	Authors	Journal
1	Cascaded neural network-based CT image processing for aortic root analysis	Nina Krüger; Alexander Meyer; Lennart Tautz; Markus Hüllebrand; Isaac Wamala; Marius Pullig; Markus Kofler; Jörg Kempfert; Simon Sündermann; Volkmar Falk; Anja Hennemuth	International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery, 17 (3)
2	Geometry aware physics informed neural network surrogate for solving Navier–Stokes equation (GAPINN)	Jan Oldenburg; Finja Borowski; Alper Öner; Klaus-Peter Schmitz; Michael Stiehm	Advanced Modeling and Simulation in Engineering Sciences
3	Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic in silico drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility	Flora T. Musuamba, Ine Skottheim Rusten, Raphaëlle Lesage, Giulia Russo, Roberta Bursi, Luca Emili, Gaby Wangorsch, Efthymios Manolis, Kristin E. Karlsson, Alexander Kulesza, Eulalie Courcelles, Jean-Pierre Boissel, Cécile F. Rousseau, Emmanuelle M. Voisin, Rossana Alessandrello, Nuno Curado, Enrico Dall'ara, Blanca Rodriguez, Francesco Pappalardo, Liesbet Geris.	CPT: Pharmacometrics & Systems Pharmacology
4	Computation of flow through TAVI device by means of physics informed neural networks	Oldenburg, Jan, Borowski, Finja, Schmitz, Klaus-Peter and Stiehm, Michael.	Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering
5	Validation of a Fluid Structure Interaction Model for TAVR using Particle Image Velocimetry	Finja Borowski, Robert Ott, Jan Oldenburg, Sebastian Kaule, Alper Öner, Klaus-Peter Schmitz, Michael Stiehm	Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering
6	Analysis of thrombosis risk of commissural misaligned transcatheter aortic valve prostheses using particle image velocimetry	Finja Borowski, Sebastian Kaule, Jan Oldenburg, Klaus-Peter Schmitz, Alper Öner and Michael Stiehm	tm - Technisches Messen
7	Analysis on the effects of hypo-attenuated leaflet thickening on the hemodynamics of transcatheter aortic valve prostheses by means of particle image velocimetry	Oldenburg, Jan, Borowski, Finja, Kaule, Sebastian, Schmitz, Klaus-Peter, Öner, Alper and Stiehm, Michael.	tm - Technisches Messen
8	Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey	Lesage, R., Van Oudheusden, M., Schievano, S., Van Hoyweghen, I., Geris, L., Capelli, C.	Frontiers in Medical Technology
9	Critical time-step size analysis and mass scaling by ghost-penalty for immersogeometric explicit dynamics	Stein K.F. Stoter, Sai C. Divi, E. Harald van Brummelen, Mats G. Larson, Frits de Prenter, Clemens V. Verhoosel	Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering
10	Feasibility Assessment of Using CDISC Data Standards for in vivo and in silico Medical Device Trials	Aydin, Burç & Kiely, Eanna & Ohmann, Christian. (2023).	Journal of the Society of Clinical Data Management
11	In-silico enhanced animal study of pulmonary artery pressure sensors: assessing hemodynamics using computational fluid dynamics	Jan Brüning, Pavlo Yevtushenko, Adriano Schlieff, Tobias Jochum, Livia van Gijzen, Sonja Meine, Jan Romberg, Titus Kuehne, Andreas Arndt, Leonid Goubergrits	Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine
12	Generation of synthetic aortic valve stenosis geometries for in silico trials	Verstraeten, S., Hoeijmakers, M., Tonino, P., Bruening, J., Capelli, C., van de Vosse, F., Huberts, W.	International Journal of Numerical Methods in

			Biomedical Engineering
13	Efficient sensitivity analysis for biomechanical models with correlated inputs	Pjotr L. J. Hilhorst, Sjeng Quicken, Frans N. van de Vosse, Wouter Huberts	International Journal of Numerical Methods in Biomedical Engineering
14	CT-based comparison of porcine, ovine, and human pulmonary arterial morphometry	Goubergrits L., Schafstedde M., Cesarovic N., Szengel A., Schmitt B., Wiegand M., Romberg J., Arndt A., Kuehne T., Brüning J.,	Nature Scientific Reports
15	A fast in silico model for preoperative risk assessment of paravalvular leakage	Michelle Spanjaards, Finja Borowski, Laura Supp, René Ubachs, Valentina Lavezzo & Olaf van der Sluis	Biomechanics and Modeling in Mechanobiology

Table 1: SIMCor journal articles.

Conference papers

N	Title	Authors	Conference
1	Identification of the most influential factors on pulmonary artery hemodynamics using variance-based sensitivity analysis	Moradi, Hamed; Van de Vosse, Frans; Huberts, Wouter	VPH2022 Abstract Book
2	Computer modelling and simulation in clinics: mapping usage and opinions for advancing in silico medicine	Raphaelle Lesage; Michiel Van Oudheusden; Martina Contin; Silvia Schievano; Liesbet Geris; Claudio Capelli	VPH2022 Abstract Book
3	Non-parametric statistical shape modelling for in silico trials of TAVI	Verstraeten, Sabine; Suasso de Lima de Prado, Damián; Hoeijmakers, Martijn; Van de Vosse, Frans; Huberts, Wouter	VPH2022 Abstract Book
4	Sensitivity analysis of an one-dimensional pulse wave propagation model with correlated input	Hilhorst, Pjotr; Quicken, Sjeng; Van de Vosse, Frans; Huberts, Wouter	VPH2022 Abstract Book
5	Validation of a Synthetic Cohort of Aortic Stenosis Patients	Brüning, Jan; Yevtushenko, Pavlo; Goubergrits, Leonid	VPH2022 Abstract Book
6	Assessment of Thrombogenic Potential of Prosthetic Heart Valves based on Particle Image Velocimetry Measurements	Finja Borowski, Jan Oldenburg, Sebastian Kaule, Klaus-Peter Schmitz, Alper Öner, Michael Stiehm	GALA - German Association of Laser Anemometry - 30th Annual Congress 2022
7	Measurement of Steady Flow through a Transcatheter Aortic Valve Replacement by means of Particle Image Velocimetry	Jan Oldenburg, Finja Borowski, Sebastian Kaule, Alper Öner, Klaus-Peter Schmitz and Michael Stiehm	GALA - German Association of Laser Anemometry - 30th Annual Congress 2022
8	Potential of using shell elements methods in FSI simulations of pulmonary arteries	Moradi, H., van de Vosse, F., Huberts, W	28th Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB2023)
9	Inter-species differences in pulmonary artery morphometry and hemodynamics	Brüning, J., Krüger, N., Yevtushenko, P., Goubergrits, L.	28th Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB2023)
10	Virtual cohort generation for in silico trials of transcatheter aortic valve implantation	Verstraeten, S., Hoeijmakers, M., van de Vosse, F., Huberts, W.	28th Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB2023)
11	Pre-operative risk assessment of paravalvular leakage using a computational TAVI deployment model	Spanjaards, M., Borowski, F., Supp, L., Ubachs, R., Lavezzo, V., Van der Sluis, O	28th Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB2023)
12	CFD-based synthetic data generation for machine learning based pressure drop assessment in aortic stenosis	Teodor Ionut Matei, Andreea Bianca Popescu, Cosmin Ioan Nita, Costin Florian Ciusdel, Lucian Mihai Itu	28th Annual Conference of the European Society of Biomechanics (ESB2023)
13	Deep Learning-based Pulmonary Artery Surface Mesh Generation	Nina Krüger, Jan Brüning, Leonid Goubergrits, Matthias Ivantsits, Lars Walczak, Volkmar Falk, Henryk Dreger, Titus Kühne, Anja Hennemuth	STACOM 2023
14	A Bayesian framework for uncertainty estimation and calibration of the expected behavior of simple materials (Submitted)	M.P. Wollner, M. Rolf-Pissarczyk, G.A. Holzapfel	Computational Mechanics

Table 2: SIMCor conference papers.

Book chapters

Title	Authors	Book
Scan-Based Immersed Isogeometric Flow Analysis.	Verhoosel, C. V., Harald van Brummelen, E., Divi, S. C., & de Prenter, F. (2023).	Frontiers in Computational Fluid-Structure Interaction and Flow Simulation: Research from Lead Investigators Under Forty-2023, 477-512.

Table 3: SIMCor book chapters.

Publications planned/in progress

N	Partner	Title/Topic
1	CHA	Comparison of the human, ovine, and porcine pulmonary artery hemodynamics.
2	TUE	A model of heart failure patients for the generation of an in silico cohort
3	TUE	The potential of using shell element methods in FSI simulations of pulmonary arteries
4	IHS	Theoretical framework for socio-economic impact assessment
5	PHI	Pre-operative risk assessment of paravalvular leakage using a computational TAVI deployment implantation model
6	TUG	Integration of the VRE with the statistical environment and the virtual cohort generator
7	UCL	Statistical shape modelling
8	IHS	Scoping Review on impacts of in-silico technologies for medical devices on firm, market, health system and society
9	TUG	Regional-specific biaxial response and microstructural of pulmonary arteries and ascending aortas from mammals and humans
10	TUG	Credibility assessment of a scaffold model for biodegradable heart valves in a hierarchical system according to ASME V&V40
11	BIO	Designing and testing an implantable sensor with in-silico techniques

Table 4: SIMCor publications planned/in progress.